

Spectrophotometric Estimation of Lac Dye

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The spectrophotometric estimation of the actual dye content in lac dye samples for use in lac industrial units is reported.

Lac dye is obtained in approx. 1% yield on the weight of sticklac used during the processing of sticklac to shellac¹. There is a growing demand for this dye, particularly in the manufacture of beverages, confectioneries, drugs², cosmetics³ and in the textile industry for producing attractive shades with different mordants⁴. The present investigation was aimed at developing a fast, accurate and inexpensive analytical method for estimating the actual dye content in lac dye samples which are obtained primarily from factory effluents of lac industrial units.

Results and Discussion

It has been established⁵ that lac dye is composed of at least 5 components, designated as laccaic acids A, B, C, D and E. Laccaic acids A and E together constitute 90% of the dye. It was also pointed out that the electronic spectrum of laccaic acid A has a close resemblance to that of the dye as a whole. Earlier work has shown⁶ that the dye has two prominent maxima at 292 and 490 nm in water. However, it was observed by us that the absorption at 490 nm was actually at 488.5 nm.

Sensitivity : The plot of absorbance vs concentration revealed that Beers law is valid over a concentration range 0.00016–0.032% (1.6–320 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The optimum concentration range for estimation as determined from the Ringbom plot^{7,8} was found to be 0.0008–0.008% (8–80 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The molar absorptivity was 5182 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 488.5 nm in water.

Effect of diverse ions : Lac dye is normally isolated as its insoluble calcium salt⁹, which is decomposed by mineral acid to yield pure dye. The effect of Ca^{2+} , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions on the calibration curve of the dye was therefore studied by adding varying amounts of CaCl_2 , HCl and H_2SO_4 to the test solutions. There was no perceptible change in the absorbance curve of lac dye in the presence of these ions.

Experimental

A Hitachi U 2000 uv-visible spectrophotometer was used. The lac dye (100 mg) was prepared as per reported procedure⁸. The dye was warmed with water (25 ml) on a water-bath. The partially dissolved dye was decanted and the process was repeated with the residue until no more material went into solution. The dye solution was filtered and weighed to constant weight. The solutions of different concentrations (0.00008, 0.00016, 0.00032, 0.00048% etc.) were prepared by appropriate dilution of the original stock

solution. Absorbances of the test solution was measured at 488.5 nm against water as a blank.

Application : Lac dye sample (1 g) was dissolved in aq. NaOH (10%, 3 ml), diluted with water (20 ml) and heated on a water bath for 15 min. The violet colored solution was acidified with 10% HCl (20%) to pH 2–2.5. The dye solution was further diluted to 1000 ml, 25 ml of this solution was made upto the 250 ml. An aliquot (50 ml) was withdrawn, filtered and its absorbance was measured at 488.5 nm against water as a blank.

Precision and accuracy : A standard solution of lac dye (0.0008%) was estimated 20 times against the calibration curve of lac dye by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.078 with a standard deviation of ± 0.001 and a coefficient of variation of $\pm 1.15\%$. The method was tested on a number of samples obtained from industry as well as prepared in the laboratory. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—LAC DYE CONTENT OF SOME SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Sample	Actual lac dye content (%)
1.	D. M. Shellac Factory (M.P.) (Lac Dye)	53.0
2.	Gupta Shellac Factory (Bihar) (Lac mud)	45.6
3.	ILRI Calcium salt of lac dye (Acidification with HCl)	69.0
4.	ILRI Calcium salt of lac dye (Acidification with H_2SO_4)	46.0
5.	Gupta Shellac Factory (Bihar) (Calcium salt of lac dye)	2.0
6.	D.M. Shellac Factory (M.P.) (Crude lac dye)	50.0
7.	BISCOLAMF (Bihar) (Calcium salt of lac dye)	7.0
8.	ILRI waste lac dye sample	8.0
9.	'Lac Pure Red' (National Handloom Dev. Corp.)	4.5
10.	'Lac Purple' (National Handloom Dev. Corp.)	10.0
11.	ILRI 'Pure' lac dye	80.0
12.	ILRI Calcium salt of lac dye (From lac mud)	39.0

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